

Leave Credit Management System Using Decision Tree Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

This study is a web-based application designed to assist the human resource management office in managing leave credit. This research aims to optimize and computerize the manual process of leave application and give an automatic procedure based on the decision tree model developed by the researcher. This study aims to develop a Leave Credit Management System using Decision Tree Algorithm specifically to identify the problems encountered in the present leave credit system, to develop a decision tree model that will be implemented in the proposed leave credit management system, to determine the benefits or advantages of the proposed leave credit management system using the decision support system; and to assess or evaluate the proposed decision support system for leave credit management system using decision tree model using ISO/IEC 9126 standards. The system was developed with the PHP programming language and the MySQL database. The system was designed and developed utilizing the Agile Methodology to cope with the design and implementation efficiently. The system's usefulness is a significant boost in production, which resulted in Highly Accepted.

Keywords: *Decision Support System, Decision Tree Model, Leave Credit, Management System*

INTRODUCTION

A Leave Credit Management System has evolved in many sectors, with numerous tools and features utilized to aid the firm in keeping track of and recording employee leave in the human resource office (Warner & Wäger, 2019).

Leave Credit Management System (LCMS) is an information system used in the Human Resource Department. LCMS is used by the employee when he/she applies for Leave, such as vacation leave, sick leave, birthday leave, Special Leave, and others. The employee or applicant must fill out the form completely. The Human Resources staff will then check if the form is complete, compute the remaining leave credits, and deduct the applied number of days granted (Tripathi, 2011).

Decision Support Systems (DSS) are computer-based information systems that play a significant part in selecting one of the various alternative solutions to problems in the leave credit management system. Automating some of the decision-making processes in a significant, computer-based DSS is feasible, allowing it to examine enormous amounts of data more quickly. It assists the company in boosting its market share, lowering expenses, increasing profitability, and improving quality. The nature of the problem itself is vital in the decision-making process (Fotich & Marcial, 2015).

The present procedures or processes in applying for Leave in the University of La Salette, Inc. – College Department are done manually using paper-based processing; they need the approval of the top administration. It is time-consuming considering reviewing the application, filling out the application form by the HR personnel, computing, and sorting the file. The development of the Decision Support for Employee Leave Credit System facilitates the easier and faster process of various leave applications.

The decision support system will save time for the person in charge of the leave credit application while examining and evaluating pre-application requirements. Additionally, processing leave requests through the leave management system will take less time and effort for the faculty, staff, and administration. The applicant will be informed via text message as to the status of their leave application after it has been approved or rejected.

Therefore, the researcher proposed an automated system of computing employees' leave credits to lessen the burden of managing and computing leave credits.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This section describes the steps or procedures for developing a "Leave Credit Management System using Decision Tree Algorithm." Also, it describes the models, processes, risk analysis, design, development, and acceptance testing that the researcher underwent during the study.

Figure 1. Agile Software Development Cycle

The researcher used the Agile Methodology (Lowry et al., 2017) technique used on the project from the planning phase through the end of the stage, and it is to guarantee that all functional and user requirements, as well as organization strategic goals and objectives, are accomplished. Furthermore, the researcher utilized the decision tree model to classify the leave application from pre-application to the end of the leave application procedure.

Respondents. This study involved 53 participants who evaluated the system, including the human resource Staff team, top administration, faculty, and staff.

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher used three different data collection methods. The researcher began gathering data by reading related resources from numerous journals, books, documents, and websites on the internet. During the design phase, a series of interviews with participants was undertaken to gather needs and benchmark with international and local organizations that utilize the same application system. Based on the inputs gathered, the researchers designed a prototype for testing and gathered user feedback to enhance the system before its complete deployment. When the system was ready for implementation, a survey questionnaire was distributed to users in order to assess the quality of the implemented Leave Credit Management system.

Data Analysis Procedure. In the analysis of the data gathered the diagram was used to present the schema of these data. Diagrams are also used to present the transformation of data obtained from the survey questionnaire floated by the participants of this study were tabulated and analyzed employing a 4-point Likert scale of 1 to 4 with numerical interpretation as 1 – not acceptable, 2 – acceptable, 3 – very acceptable, and 4 – highly acceptable. A weighted mean formula was used to analyze the data obtained from the questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Development of decision tree model of the proposed Leave Credit Management System using Decision Tree Algorithm

The features of the in-house developed Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Algorithm

The development environment in a computer program and software product development is the collection of processes and programming tools used to develop the program or software product. The researcher used the following programming tools environments to create the Decision Support System for Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Model: PHP, Javascript, AJAX, and Bootstrap CSS. Similarly, the researcher used MySQL as a tool to create the system's database as a backend.

Figure 1. Login form

The figure represents the system's login form. Here, the authorized user enters his or her login and password. When a user enters the correct login and password, he or she is taken to the system's main form.

Figure 2. Application form for Leave

The figure shows the leave application, where the user may control the employee's pre-application. In contrast, in this module, the system can classify the employee's leave application if he or she is eligible for a particular sort of Leave.

Figure 3. Leave Monitoring Form

The figure shows the Leave Credit monitoring, where the user may monitor the employee's consent or leave by semester and print the report. In addition, the user can show how much leave an employee has accrued compared to the number of Leave granted in this module.

Figure 4. Leave Application for Approval

The diagrams show a list of approved leave applications. This form displays the employee's classified approved leave information.

Users' Acceptability of the System**Table 1. Mean Response of the Respondents on the Evaluation of Proposed Leave Credit Management System Using Decision Tree Algorithm in Terms of Functionality**

No.	Sub-Characteristics	Mean	Qualitative Rating
1	The system records application information.	3.62	Highly Acceptable
2	The system assesses pre-application requirements as the basis for approval of Leave.	3.50	Highly Acceptable
3	The system accurately sends SMS notification upon the approval of leave application thru classification.	3.60	Highly Acceptable
4	The system secures data through database management.	3.65	Highly Acceptable
Grand Mean		3.59	Highly Acceptable

Shows the mean response of respondents in evaluating the proposed Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Algorithm in terms of Functionality. It reveals that "the secure system data through database management" got the highest mean of 3.65, interpreted as Highly Acceptable. In contrast, "the system assesses pre-application requirements as basis of approval of leave" got the lowest mean of 3.50, also interpreted as Highly Acceptable.

The analysis indicates that the evaluation under Functionality is Highly Acceptable, with a grand mean of 3.59.

Table 2. Mean Response of the Respondents on the Evaluation of Proposed Leave Credit Management System Using Decision Tree Algorithm in Terms of Usability.

No.	Sub-Characteristics	Mean	Qualitative Rating
1	The system is equipped with message box/notification boxes	3.65	Highly Acceptable
2	The system operates with minimal effort	3.52	Highly Acceptable
3	The system's interface is appealing	3.63	Highly Acceptable
4	The system uses icons in every menu	3.20	Very Acceptable
5	Compared to other software, the system is easy to learn	3.60	Highly Acceptable
Grand Mean		3.52	Highly Acceptable

Shows the mean response of respondents in evaluating the proposed Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Algorithm in terms of Usability. It reveals that "the system equipped with message box/ notification boxes" got the highest mean of 3.65, interpreted as Highly Acceptable. In contrast, "the system uses icons in every menu" got the lowest mean of 3.20, also interpreted as Very Acceptable.

The analysis indicates that the evaluation under Usability is Highly Acceptable, with a grand mean of 3.52.

Table 3. Mean Response of the Respondents on the Evaluation of Proposed Leave Credit Management System Using Decision Tree Algorithm in Terms of Reliability

No.	Sub-Characteristics	Mean	Qualitative Rating
1	The system uses trapping scripts to secure proper data is stored	3.52	Highly Acceptable
2	The system is capable of activating or deactivating user/ account	3.61	Highly Acceptable
3	The system tracks creation and modification of data	3.24	Very Acceptable
Grand Mean		3.46	Highly Acceptable

Shows the mean response of respondents in evaluating the proposed Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Algorithm in terms of Reliability. It reveals that "the system is capable of activating or deactivating user/account" got the highest mean of 3.61, interpreted as Highly Acceptable. In contrast, "the system tracts creation and modification of data" got the lowest mean of 3.24, also interpreted as Very Acceptable.

The analysis indicates that the evaluation under Reliability is Highly Acceptable, with a grand mean of 3.46.

Table 4. Mean Response of the Respondents on the Evaluation of Proposed Leave Credit Management System Using Decision Tree Algorithm in Terms of Efficiency

No.	Sub-Characteristics	Mean	Qualitative Rating
1	The system responds promptly.	3.25	Very Acceptable
2	The system accomplishes the task quickly.	3.50	Highly Acceptable
3	The use of the system enhances the effectiveness of the leave application.	3.52	Highly Acceptable
4	The system generates timely information.	3.69	Highly Acceptable
5	The system has more concise and summarized information.	3.46	Very Acceptable
Grand Mean		3.48	Highly Acceptable

Shows the mean response of respondents in evaluating the proposed Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Algorithm in terms of Efficiency. It reveals that "system generates timely information" got the highest mean of 3.69, interpreted as Highly Acceptable. In contrast, "the system responds promptly" got the lowest mean of 3.25, also interpreted as Very Acceptable.

The analysis indicates that the evaluation under Efficiency is Highly Acceptable, with a grand mean of 3.48.

Table 5. Mean Response of the Respondents on the Evaluation of Proposed Leave Credit Management System Using Decision Tree Algorithm in Terms of Portability

No.	Sub-Characteristics	Mean	Qualitative Rating
1	The system is capable of changing/managing user roles	3.48	Highly Acceptable
2	Installation of the system is done effortlessly	3.60	Highly Acceptable
Grand Mean		3.54	Highly Acceptable

Shows the mean response of respondents in evaluating the proposed Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Algorithm in terms of Portability. It reveals that "installation of the system done effortlessly" got the highest mean of 3.60, interpreted as Highly Acceptable. In contrast, "the system is capable of changing/ managing user roles" got the lowest mean of 3.48, also interpreted as Highly Acceptable.

The analysis indicates that the evaluation under Portability is Highly Acceptable, with a grand mean of 3.54.

Table 6. Grand Mean Response of the Respondents on the Evaluation of Proposed Leave Credit Management System Using Decision Tree Algorithm

Parameter	Total Value	Mean	Qualitative Rating
Functionality	3.59		Highly Acceptable
Usability	3.52		Highly Acceptable
Reliability	3.46		Highly Acceptable
Efficiency	3.48		Highly Acceptable
Portability	3.54		Highly Acceptable
GRAND TOTAL MEAN	3.518		Highly Acceptable

Shows the grand mean response of respondents in evaluating the proposed Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Algorithm in terms of Functionality, Usability, Reliability, Efficiency, and Portability. It reveals that Functionality got the highest total mean of 3.59, interpreted as Highly Acceptable, while Reliability got the lowest total mean of 3.46, also interpreted as Highly Acceptable.

The analysis indicates that the overall evaluation of the proposed Leave Credit Management System using the Decision Tree Algorithm is Highly Acceptable, with a total mean of 3.518.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concludes that using a Leave Credit Management System using a Decision Tree Algorithm is commendable to support a faster way of managing the leave credit system and classification of leave applications. The system's usefulness is to radically increase production, lessen time consumption and eliminate repetitive processes. Based on the result gathered, the acceptability of the system problems identified were well addressed. The system can classify the leave application from pre-application up to the classification by the president. The pilot of the study/ the agency can also ensure their data security through database integration. Also, the system provides accurate reports generated and offers time generation. Ultimately, the operation results were considered highly acceptable based on the agency's perception.

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